

An Introduction to Building the DengX Framework for Dengue Forecasting

To any public health professionals who use “Artificial Intelligence” on a regular basis but are also not entirely sure how it works or what it does—then the book, *AI Snake Oil*, by Narayanan and Kapoor should be on the top of your “read later” list. The authors provide a succinct and useful overview of types of AI, limitations they have, what kind of tasks they can complete, what their future uses might be, and very importantly—How do you know if an AI tool actually works as described or if it is *Snake Oil* (1)?

The book also includes a thought-provoking evaluation of **Predictive AI**—questioning its usefulness and accuracy, concluding that predictive AI does not work. The reasoning is based on example cases where predictive AI was used, showed promising results, but on closer evaluation were often not accurate. From this they say that not only does predictive AI usually not work, but it most likely never will (1). In this text we disagree with this position and present a counter-point—**Predictive AI can be useful given appropriate application.**

Predictive AI, as examined in the book, focuses (with few exceptions) on predicting human behaviour. However, how does one design research that can predict human behaviour? Behaviour is a complex phenomenon driven by a multitude of interacting dependent-independent variable nexuses. The extent to which neurobiology and external stimuli interact to produce behaviour is an area of knowledge yet to be fully understood. Let say, for example, that a company wishes to predict how much cereal they will sell over time. To answer this research question, they must decipher “What makes someone buy this specific brand of cereal?”. Perhaps it’s the colour of the box, or a comprehensive ad campaign. Maybe coupons were used to incentivise purchases, or the nutritional value is superior to its competition. The company would then use these independent variables to predict sale numbers. This works by a machine learning model developing and implementing algorithmic steps tailored to the data used, which in turn generates a predicted version of the dependent variable. The problem is that we do not know if the relationship “found” by the model is random or founded in reality. Do specific coloured cereal boxes trigger cereal-purchasing neurotransmitters? Do socioeconomic class have a deterministic impact on who will buy the cereal? To what extent do we purchase cereal based on stochastic processes such as which entrance to the grocery a customer uses, and thus what brand of cereal is seen first. If our understanding of how variables drive purchase behaviour is limited, then how do we know if a relationship is spurious or genuine? —the simple answer is, we cannot (at least not yet).

The limitation to predictive AI is not due to an inability to predict the future but is instead due to fantastical research questions founded on nonempirical research design. This becomes clear when the authors present the exception to their position on predictive AI—the CDCs annual FluSight competition. They write:

“Every year, the Center for Disease Control (CDC) forecasts how the flu season is going to play out, which helps healthcare providers better prepare for any potential surge in patients. We have a pretty good idea of how good these forecasts are because the CDC runs an open competition called FluSight. The models in the competition have consistently gotten better over the years. They are much more accurate than using simple baselines like the number of cases that occurred in a given week and region in the previous flu cycle.”

The major difference between predicting flu cases versus cereal sales is that flu is predicted using measurable variables that are derived via the scientific process. The winning FluSight model, *Flusion*, used seasonal influenza disease activity from multiple data sources.

The model, which utilises gradient boosting, used 114 x features. This included seasonality, data source, location, the curvature of the surveillance signal in the weeks leading up, etc (2).

The biological relationship between flu cases and these variables is based on decades of surveillance data, vaccine development, investigation of flu mutations, transmission momentum, and more. From this, we have come to better understand the What, How, and Why of the flu—allowing for the evidence-based design of FluSight models.

The success of FluSight (and many more such studies) highlight the conditions necessary for predictive AI to be effective in public health. From this we can derive the following: 1) To use Predictive AI, the phenom of study should be well understood, as should the forces that drive it. Based on further research in this field we propose two additional points: 2) Predictive AI requires access to data sufficient in temporal resolution, accuracy, and non-zero dominance (that optimally supports geospatial analysis). 3) Data selection and research design should be informed by a well conducted literature review on the phenom in question (3).

Research into the dengue-climate nexus has employed Predictive AI, with encouraging results. However, a structured framework is needed to standardise research design to ensure accurate and useful evidence generation. To build on my current work with the dengue-climate nexus for the non-Latin Caribbean, I will carry out a series of studies with the goal of developing a template for dengue-climate nexus research. The purpose of this is to build a framework for dengue forecasting—the **DengX** framework.

References

- (1) Narayanan A, Kapoor S. AI Snake Oil: What Artificial Intelligence Can Do, What It Can't, and How to Tell the Difference. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press; 2024.
- (2) Ray EL, Wang Y, Wolfinger RD, Reich NG. Flusion: integrating multiple data sources for accurate influenza predictions. *Journal of Computational Science*. 2025 Jan 15;81:102363.
- (3) Bengtsson-Asgarali D. Designing Dengue-Climate Nexus Research for Machine Learning Modeling. Zenodo; 2026.